

A Modified Micro-method for the Estimation of Nitrogen in Soil.

BY SRISH KUMAR SAHA.

In course of the analysis of a number of soil samples containing a low percentage of nitrogen, it appeared to us to be of interest to ascertain the applicability and also the accuracy of Micro-Kjeldahl methods for such estimation. A number of parallel experiments showed that the results of micro- and macro-estimations were absolutely concordant.

The samples were dried at 100°-110° and passed through a sieve of 100 mesh. In view of the low percentage of nitrogen, 0.1 to 0.2 g. of each sample was weighed out in an ordinary analytical balance. The rest of the procedure was exactly as in Pregel's Micro-Kjeldahl. The final titrations were made with N/70 solutions with Wesslow's indicator (methylene blue-methyl red). The results are given below in a tabular form.

No. of sample.	Macro-estimation according to the method of A. O. A. C.		Micro-estimation	
	Wt. taken.	% N.	% N.	Wt. taken.
1	6.653 g.	0.1840	0.1837	0.1443
2	7.8717	0.1621	0.1620	0.1510
3	6.5230	0.1577	0.158	0.1356
4	5.5472	0.5082	0.508	0.0728
5			0.28	0.1645
6			0.182	0.2139
7			0.376	0.1704
8			0.243	0.1525
9			0.0442	0.2030
10			0.0367	0.1364

My thanks are due to Sir P. C. Ray for the kind interest he has taken in this work.